

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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DESCRIPTION OF METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AN ENTERPRISE

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Abstract: This article considers determining the position of an enterprise in the studied market, developing measures to increase competitiveness, selecting counterparties for joint activities, drawing up a program for entering new sales markets, implementing investment activities, and implementing state regulation of the economy.

Key words: enterprise, market, counterparty, competition, program, investment, methodology.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur makolada o'rganilayotgan bozorda korxonaning mavqeini aniqlash, raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqish, birgalikdagi faoliyat uchun kontragentlarni tanlash, yangi sotish bozorlariga chiqish dasturini tuzish, investitsiya faoliyatini amalga oshirish, iqtisodiyotni davlat tomonidan tartibga solishni amalga oshirish ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: korxonona, bozor, kontragent, raqobat, dastur, investitsiya, metodologiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье речь идет об определении положения компании на изучаемом рынке, разработке мер по повышению конкурентоспособности, выборе контрагентов для совместной деятельности, создании программы выхода на новые рынки сбыта, осуществлении инвестиционной деятельности, осуществлении государственного регулирования экономики.

Ключевые слова: Предприятие, рынок, контрагент, конкуренция, программа, инвестиции, методология.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the most pressing issues are to increase the range and quality of goods produced, ensure their stable sales in domestic and foreign markets, increase competitiveness in a highly competitive environment, extend the life of goods, create new product designs based on market demand, strengthen the position of local goods, and ensure their brand recognition.

The main goal of the „Strategy for the Development of Competition in Commodity and Financial Markets for 2020-2024“ established by our President is to stimulate economic growth and innovation, increase investment flows, and create new jobs by creating effectively functioning markets and a healthy competitive environment. This is also aimed at developing relations between economic entities.

Along with theoretical studies of the essence of competition and competitiveness, the problem of practical assessment of competitiveness has been discussed in economic literature for a long time. It can be said that certain achievements have been made in assessing the competitiveness of products to date, and the competitiveness of the same goods and services has been assessed.

Very acceptable methods of assessment have been developed. At the same time, it should be noted that the issue of assessing the competitiveness of enterprises remains complex. Despite the fact that certain steps have been taken and are being taken in this direction, economists have not yet developed a universal and generally recognized methodology for comprehensively assessing the competitiveness of an enterprise.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE TOPIC

Based on foreign experience, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their application in practice. Among them, we can include such famous scientists as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory in the economy. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Paradaev, R. Ibragimov, YO. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musaeva and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research process used a systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and selective observation methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At the same time, in a market economy, the need to assess the competitiveness of enterprises, to assess their competitive positions remains an integral element of the activities of any business entity. The study of competitors and competitive conditions in the industry is important for the enterprise, first of all, to determine what its advantages and disadvantages are over competitors and to draw conclusions so that the enterprise can develop its own successful competitive strategy and maintain its competitive advantage. Determining the competitiveness of an enterprise is an integral element of the activities of any business entity.

In particular, it provides for the following objectives for assessing the competitiveness of an economic entity:

- development of measures to increase competitiveness;
- selection of counterparties for joint activities;
- drawing up a program for entering new sales markets;
- implementation of investment activities;
- implementation of state regulation of the economy.

In any case, the main goal of assessing the competitiveness of an enterprise is to determine the position of the enterprise in the market under study.

The main task of every economist studying the problem of assessing the competitiveness of enterprises is to find the criteria for competitiveness, its sources and factors. Analysis of the economic literature on the topic under consideration made it possible to identify several approaches to solving the set tasks. In addition, the main known methods of assessing the competitiveness of companies were analyzed, their advantages and disadvantages were summarized.

Speaking about the classification of existing methods, first of all, it is necessary to note that there are a lot of different methods for assessing the competitiveness of enterprises by economists. According to these methods, they are classified according to their many characteristics, according to their theoretical content, according to the interpretation of the assessment results, according to the form of mathematical correlation of indicators, etc. Within the framework of this study, a meaningful (classical) classification of methods for assessing the competitiveness of companies is analyzed. The study considers only the main (widespread) methods of assessing the competitiveness of enterprises at present. Thus, the following main methods for assessing the competitiveness of enterprises can be distinguished.

The essence of this type of method is that solving the problem of assessing the competitiveness of an enterprise, in a market economy, the competition of companies takes the form of product competition, and the competitiveness of a company within a certain product market directly depends on the competitiveness of its products. The appropriateness of this position has been repeatedly confirmed in economic practice, that is, the competitiveness of companies in the market is demonstrated by their competitive products. On the contrary, it is difficult to imagine a successful enterprise that produces products that are not in demand among consumers. Within the framework of this approach, the connection between product competitiveness and the success of the company is so strong that these categories are practically defined.

Product methods are based on the conclusion that the assessment of the competitiveness of an economic entity can be carried out by assessing the competitiveness of its products: the higher the competitiveness of the product, the higher the competitiveness of the enterprise. At the same time, various marketing and qualitative methods are used to determine the competitiveness of products, most of which are based on the price-quality ratio of products. There are many methods for finding this ratio. Below is a brief description of the most common of them.

The competitiveness indicator of an enterprise is determined, as a rule, by finding the average value among the competitiveness indicators for each type of product, where the sales volume of the corresponding type of product is used as a weight:

$$K = \sum a_i \cdot k_i \quad (1.1)$$

K – competitiveness of the enterprise;

$oh\ my$ – the share of the i -th type of product in the total volume of products sold;

$that$ – Competitiveness of the i -th type of product.

The calculation of competitiveness indicators for each of the products is carried out through economic and parametric indices:

$$k_i = \frac{\Pi}{\Theta} \quad (1.2)$$

$that$ – competitiveness of the i -type product;

P – parametric index;

E – economic index.

The parametric index reflects the weighting of the indices of individual specific parameters of the analyzed product relative to a competing (benchmark) product, taking into account the corresponding coefficient:

$$\Pi = \sum b_i \cdot p_i \quad (1.3)$$

P – parametric index;

$this$ – weight coefficient of the i -parameter;

pi – the specific index of the i -parameter of the product.

In turn, each of the partial indices for the corresponding parameter is calculated as the ratio of the actual value of the estimated parameter of the analyzed product to the value of the corresponding indicator of the competing product (or a suitable benchmark product selected as a comparison base). The list of estimated parameters of the product, as well as the weight coefficient of each parameter, is determined by expert opinion.

$$p_i = \frac{\xi_a}{\xi_b} \quad (1.4)$$

pi – the specific index of the i -parameter of the product;

to – the actual true value of the parameter being evaluated;

yes – the reference value of the parameter being evaluated.

The economic index of the analyzed product is defined as the ratio of all its consumption-related costs to the consumption costs of a competing (benchmark) product.

$$\Theta = \frac{Z_a}{Z_b} \quad (1.5)$$

E – economic index;

Za – total consumption costs of the product under analysis;

Ze – consumption costs of the benchmark.

Total consumption costs include the costs of the product itself and its use, the purchase of consumables, maintenance (including repairs) and disposal.

It should be noted that some researchers suggest using the market share of a product as an indicator of product competitiveness, which, in our opinion, more accurately reflects competitiveness.

Among the undoubted advantages of the approach under consideration is the fact that it is one of the important components of the competitiveness of the enterprise.

- taking into account the competitiveness of its products.

Indeed, it is difficult to imagine a successful enterprise without a competitive product portfolio.

The disadvantages are that the competitiveness of products is still not the same as the sustainable competitive advantage of the enterprise, since any price or quality advantages are relatively quickly absorbed by competitors and the economic benefits derived from them are lost. Also, there are certain criticisms that when assessing the competitiveness of products according to the price-quality ratio, the innovation-related aspects of the product, which are of great importance in placing it on the market, are not taken into account, which leads to a decrease in the level of competitiveness.

In addition, the use of the considered group of methods involves the comparison of similar products. At the same time, the development of commodity-money relations leads to increasingly sharp differences in the economic conditions of the activities of enterprises, their greater diversification and greater differentiation of goods and services. It is becoming increasingly difficult to determine the exact geographical boundaries of a

particular market, to compile a list of competing goods, which leads to a low level of application of such methods for assessing the competitiveness of enterprises.

However, the main disadvantage of this approach is that it gives a very limited idea of the advantages and disadvantages of the enterprise, since its competitiveness takes the form of product competitiveness, and other aspects of its activities are not taken into account. Because the competitiveness of products reflects the level of demand for products, and the competitiveness of the enterprise is the level of economic activity efficiency. It is not for nothing that in economic practice there are many examples of economic entities facing a crisis when they produce competitive products. The reason for this is the existence of a fundamental contradiction between the competitiveness of the enterprise and the competitiveness of its products.

The fact is that the competitiveness of products is assessed primarily from the point of view of satisfying the needs of the buyer. The competitiveness of an enterprise is assessed from the point of view of the interests of the owner of the business entity (management, investor). In other words, the lower the price of the product, the higher its competitiveness. However, whether such a price can provide the necessary economic efficiency for further expanded reproduction of the enterprise? This is a big question. Even an enterprise that chronically produces the most unique products cannot be competitive. Therefore, we consider it fundamentally wrong to assess the competitiveness of an economic entity only by assessing the competitiveness of its products, and it should be borne in mind that the approach presented here is intended only for a detailed discussion of the issue of the relationship between the competitiveness of an enterprise and the competitiveness of its products.

Indeed, since an important aspect of industrial economics is the improvement of product production, it was considered important to pay due attention to it. Therefore, in the first half of the 20th century, the essence of assessing the competitiveness of an enterprise was formed within the framework of assessing the competitiveness of its products. In short, product methods are historically the first methods of assessing the competitiveness of economic entities.

With the development of the post-industrial economy, the structure of the enterprise has become much more complex than a simple assembly shop, and the number of core competencies required for a company to succeed has increased significantly. With the increase in the number of core competencies, production.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The importance of the function has inevitably begun to decline. In addition, in the modern economy, it is becoming possible to transfer the assembly of goods in the technological process to subcontractors (often located in other regions) without losing product quality. This situation is leading to the fact that the importance of parameters related to the material production process in determining the competitiveness of a company is increasingly decreasing. In such conditions, there are fundamental differences between assessing the competitiveness of an enterprise and assessing the competitiveness of its products.

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